

Derivatives of Salicylic Acid. Part II. The 3-Nitro-5-sulpho- and 5-Nitro-3-sulpho-salicylic Acids.

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Following on the preparation of the 3- and 5-nitrosalicylic acids (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 95), we proceeded to the preparation of the 3-nitro-5-sulpho- and 5-nitro-3-sulpho-salicylic acids. On examination of earlier work it appeared that, whatever the reason may be, these important acids had never been purified and analysed.

Two methods were thought of for the purpose: (a) sulphonation of the respective nitro-acids and (b) nitration of the respective sulpho-acids.

3-Nitro-5-sulphosalicylic Acid.

In attempting to sulphonate 3-nitrosalicylic acid, we used as agents (a) sulphuric acid and fuming sulphuric acid of different strengths and (b) chlorosulphonic acid, alone and in the presence of a catalytic agent (iodine, mercury, vanadium pentoxide) and we found that 3-nitrosalicylic acid resisted all our attempts. This is remarkable because the effect of the groups, -OH, -NO₂ and -CO₂H in the 3-nitrosalicylic acid might each and all be expected to lead to the introduction of the sulphonic acid group in position 5 and remarkable, also, because the sulphonic acid in question is readily produced by nitration of 5-sulphosalicylic acid.

Hirsch (*Ber.*, 1800, 33, 3240) treated 5-sulphosalicylic acid, with a mixture of nitric and sulphuric acids. Having obtained the crude acid in small amount, he prepared the barium salt, dehydrated this and analysed it. Sakellarios (*Ber.*, 1922, 55, 2946) also used a mixture of nitric and sulphuric acids: he isolated only an acid potassium salt. Thus the acid has never been isolated in quantity and purified.

The isolation of the acid requires special attention to details. In trying Hirsch's method we found (a) that the use of fuming nitric acid (and sulphuric) gives dinitrosalicylic acid: (b) that 3-nitro-5-sulphosalicylic acid is readily soluble in sulphuric acid. Hirsch, in the hope of avoiding the production of dinitrosalicylic acid, used

sulphuric acid in quantity and for that reason obtained only a small amount of the desired acid. We find that when the amount of sulphuric acid is kept down the 3-nitro-5-sulphosalicylic acid separates in good yield: on crystallisation from water, it has the composition $C_7H_5O_8NS, 4H_2O$.

The following table shows the products that we obtained from salicylic acid (20 g.) under different conditions.

H_2SO_4 .	HNO_3 .	Sulphonitro-salicylic acid.	Dinitro-salicylic acid.	Sulpho-salicylic acid.
163 g.	18 g.	Very little	Nil	10 g.
153 g.	18 g. (fuming)	Nil	28 g.	Nil
100 g.	21 g.	23 g.	Nil	Nil

The acid can also be obtained from 5-sulphosalicylic acid, using nitric acid dissolved in acetic anhydride. The solution is later poured into a solution of barium acetate when the orange salt $C_7H_3O_8NSBa, H_2O$ separates: from this the free acid can be obtained by using sulphuric acid and water.

*5-Nitro-3-sulphosalicylic Acid.**

Mandt (*Ber.*, 1877, 10, 1701) heated 5-nitrosalicylic acid together with fuming sulphuric acid when 5-nitro-3-sulphosalicylic acid separated as a solid. He did not purify the acid and did nothing with it beyond preparing and analysing the salt $(C_7H_2O_8NS)_2Ba_3, 12H_2O$.

We have prepared 5-nitro-3-sulphosalicylic acid $C_7H_5O_8NS, 2H_2O$ by Mandt's method, and also his barium salt: although this salt is phenolic it is readily formed even in neutral solution because it is highly insoluble.

The Esters.

The two acids were converted into the methyl and ethyl esters $C_6H_2(NO_2)(OH)(SO_3H)CO_2R$: they were found to be stable substances that yield salts owing to the presence of the $-SO_3H$ and $-OH$ groups. The acids and the salts are remarkable in two ways: (1) they contain no water of crystallisation; (2) they are far weaker in colour than the original acids and their corresponding salts.

* The 5-nitrosulphosalicylic acid was not obtained from 3-sulphosalicylic acid by nitration because this acid was unknown: it has since been prepared by one of us (N. W. H.).

EXPERIMENTAL.

3-Nitro-5-sulphosalicylic Acid.

Method I.—Salicylic acid (20 g.) was dissolved in sulphuric acid (d 1.8, 100 g.): the solution was allowed to stand for an hour and 5-sulphosalicylic acid separated. The mixture was cooled below 20° and nitric acid (d 1.4, 21 g.) was added to it in small instalments while the mixture was kept cool. After the addition of all the nitric acid, and when the sulphonitro-acid began to separate the mixture was cooled in a refrigerator. The solid was collected and recrystallised from water as colourless glassy needles (yield, 23 g.). As it darkens if heated rapidly, water of crystallisation was determined by heating the acid under reduced pressure first at low temperature and then at 100° . (Found: H_2O , 21.29; N, 4.39; S, 9.66. $C_7H_5O_8NS \cdot 4H_2O$ requires H_2O , 21.50; N, 4.18; S, 9.56 per cent.).

Method II.—A mixture of nitric acid (d 1.4, 5 c.c.) and acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) was cooled; to it was added anhydrous sulphosalicylic acid (5 g.). After about six hours the mixture was poured into barium acetate solution when orange crystals separated out; they were collected and boiled with strong hydrochloric acid solution. The acid barium salt was formed, collected and recrystallised. The acid was liberated using the calculated amount of sulphuric acid and recrystallised from water (yield, 4.5 g.).

(1) The *acid barium salt* was prepared by digesting the neutral salt with concentrated hydrochloric acid. It easily changes to the neutral salt if heated with water, but can be safely recrystallised from acidic solution as parallelogramic plates of yellow colour. (Found: Ba, 19.33; H_2O , 6.46. $(C_7H_4O_8NS)_2Ba \cdot 2\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires Ba, 19.44; H_2O , 6.37 per cent.).

(2) The *neutral barium salt* (orange) is difficultly soluble in water, and crystallises as long-plates: on losing water of crystallisation it turns yellow. (Found: Ba, 32.96; H_2O , 4.25. $C_7H_3O_8NSBa$, H_2O requires Ba, 32.99; H_2O , 4.32 per cent.).

Method III.—The method of Sakellarios (*loc. cit.*) was followed, that is, the nitration mixture was poured into a solution of potassium chloride (140 g. in 1400 c. c. water) except that the temperature was kept at $15-20^{\circ}$ (Sakellarios, 30°). The salts that separated were a mixture of the acid potassium salt of 3-nitro-5-sulphosalicylic acid and the potassium salt of dinitrosalicylic acid. The salts were dissolved and the solution was neutralised by potassium carbonate.

The dipotassium salt of the 3-nitro-5-sulphosalicylic acid separated first and was found to be pure.

The *acid potassium salt* was prepared by acidifying the dipotassium salt, obtained above, with hydrochloric acid. It crystallises from water as long, pale yellow plates with a molecule of water of crystallisation. The anhydrous salt is white.

The *neutral potassium salt* was prepared as above. It is moderately soluble in hot water and crystallises as shining yellow plates. It contains water of crystallisation which could not be expelled even by heating at 100° under reduced pressure. (Found : K, 22·28. $C_7H_3O_8NSK_2$, H_2O requires K, 21·88 per cent.).

The *phenolic potassium salt* was prepared by adding strong potassium hydroxide to either of the above salts. It is easily soluble in water and crystallises as hexagonal prisms of reddish-yellow colour. (Found : H_2O , 4·60 ; K, 29·13. $C_7H_2O_8NSK_3$, H_2O requires H_2O , 4·56 ; K, 29·67 per cent.).

5-Nitro-3-sulphosalicylic Acid.

This was prepared by the method of Mandt (*loc. cit.*). 5-Nitrosalicylic acid (20 g.) was dissolved in fuming sulphuric acid (19 per cent. SO_3 , 40 c. c.) and the solution was heated on the boiling water-bath for two and a half hours. When crystals began to separate, the mixture was cooled and the solid was collected on glass wool and crystallised from water : parallelogrammic plates (yield, 27 g.). The substance is deliquescent.

The crystals were dried by pressing them on a porous tile and then keeping them for a short time over calcium chloride in a desiccator. The acid was heated at 120° under reduced pressure in order to determine water of crystallisation. (Found : H_2O , 11·87 ; N, 4·71 ; S, 10·82. $C_7H_5O_8NS$, $2H_2O$ requires H_2O , 12·04 ; N, 4·68 ; S, 10·71 per cent.).

The *phenolic barium salt* ($C_7H_3O_8NS$)₂ Ba_3 , $12H_2O$ was prepared by Mandt. We obtained the salt and confirmed Mandt's formula. The salt is highly insoluble. Though it looks gelatinous under the microscope it is seen to consist of very small yellow needles.

The *neutral barium salt* was prepared by digesting Mandt's salt with strong hydrochloric acid. It is difficultly soluble in water from which it crystallises in white grains. (Found : Ba, 38·94. $C_7H_3O_8NSBa$ requires Ba, 34·48 per cent.).

The *phenolic potassium salt* was prepared by adding an excess of strong potassium hydroxide solution to the acid. It is easily

soluble in water and crystallises from it in yellow needles containing water of crystallisation. The anhydrous salt is crimson in colour. (Found, H_2O , 12.16 ; K, 27.38. $C_7H_3O_8NSK_3$, $3H_2O$ requires H_2O , 12.52 ; K, 27.18 per cent.).

The *neutral potassium salt* was prepared by neutralising the acid by potassium hydroxide solution. It is moderately soluble in water from which it crystallises as crimson needles. (Found: H_2O , 11.48 ; K, 19.96. $C_7H_3O_8NSK_2$, $2\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires H_2O , 11.72 ; K, 20.34 per cent.).

The *acid potassium salt* was prepared by adding potassium hydroxide solution to a solution of the sulphonic acid till a yellow tinge just appeared. It is difficultly soluble in water and crystallises as colourless white needles. (Found: K, 12.98. C_7H_4NSK requires K, 12.98 per cent.).

The *neutral silver salt* was prepared by adding silver nitrate to a solution of the ammonium salt. It is difficultly soluble in water, from which it crystallises as yellow plates. (Found : Ag, 44.91 ; $C_7H_3O_8NSAg_2$ requires Ag, 45.25 per cent.).

The Esters.—We converted each of the two acids into the methyl and ethyl esters, by the usual method. The esters separated from the reaction mixture as potassium salts, $C_6H_2(NO_2)(OH)(CO_2R)SO_3K$, on the addition of potassium chloride solution. They were converted into the barium salt $[C_6H_3N_2O(CO_2R)SO_3]_2Ba$ and then by means of sulphuric acid in the calculated amount into the ester. Each ester was recrystallised from a small amount of water. The esters are hygroscopic and very soluble in water and alcohol. The phenolic barium salts $[C_6H_2(NO_2)(CO_2R)SO_3]_2OBa$ are obtained on adding barium acetate solution to that of potassium salts. None of these substances, the esters, the potassium salts, and the barium salts contains water of crystallisation.

The following table shows the properties and composition of these substances :

<i>Methyl 3-Nitro-5-sulphosalicylate.</i>				
Formula.	Appearance.	Solubility in water.	Found.	Required.
$C_6H_7O_6NS$	Slender needles.	Very soluble.	86 12.08	8, 11.56 per cent.
$C_6H_5O_6NSK$	White silky needles	Difficultly soluble.	K, 12.21	K, 12.40 "
$(C_6H_4O_6NS)_2Ba$	Pale yellow needles.	Easily soluble at 100°.	Ba, 19.69	Ba, 19.92 "
$C_6H_5O_6NSBa$	Small yellow plates.	Difficultly soluble at 100°.	Ba, 33.34	Ba, 33.32 "

Ethyl 3-Nitro-5-sulphosalicylate.

Formula.	Appearance.	Solubility in water.	Found.	Required.
$C_9H_9O_3NS$	Long white needles.	Easily soluble	S, 10-89	S, 11-00 per cent.
$C_9H_9O_3NSK$	Pale white thin plates.	Difficultly soluble.	K, 11-73	K, 11-87 ..
$(C_9H_9O_3NS)_2Ba$	Long pale yellow needles.	Easily soluble at 100°.	Ba, 18-81	Ba, 19-15 ..
$C_9H_7O_3NSBa$	Microscopic yellow needles.	Difficultly soluble at 100°.	Ba, 31-99	Ba, 32-22 ..

Methyl 5-Nitro-3-sulphosalicylate.

Formula.	Appearance.	Solubility in water.	Found.	Required.
$C_8H_7O_3NS$	Long white needles.	Easily soluble.	S, 11-86	S, 11-56 per cent.
$C_8H_5O_3NSK$	Rectangular white plates.	Difficultly soluble.	K, 12-26	K, 12-40 ..
$(C_8H_5O_3NS)_2Ba$	Pale yellow needles.	Soluble at 100°.	Ba, 19-67	Ba, 19-92 ..
$C_8H_5O_3NSBa$	Pale yellow microscopic plates.	Difficultly soluble at 100°.	Ba, 33-42	Ba, 33-32 ..

Ethyl 5-Nitro-3-sulphosalicylate.

Formula.	Appearance.	Solubility in water.	Found.	Required.
$C_9H_9O_3NS$	Long white needles.	Easily soluble.	S, 10-92	S, 11-00 per cent.
$C_9H_5O_3NSK$	Hexagonal plates.	Difficultly soluble.	K, 11-86	K, 11-87 ..
$(C_9H_5O_3NS)_2Ba$	White needles.	Easily soluble at 100°.	Ba, 19-09	Ba, 19-15 ..
$C_9H_7O_3NSBa$	Pale yellow grains.	Difficultly soluble at 100°.	Ba, 31-93	Ba, 32-22 ..